

Infrastructure as a Key Determinant of Rural Development in Petrich Municipality (Bulgaria)

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ABSTRACT

This study examines infrastructure as a key determinant of socio-economic development in rural areas within Petrich Municipality (Bulgaria), in the context of the Integrated Development Plan (2021–2027). The analysis is based on official strategic and statistical data, focusing on transport, water supply and sewerage, energy, and telecommunications infrastructure. The findings demonstrate that infrastructure provision is directly linked to quality of life, accessibility of services, economic activity, and demographic dynamics in rural areas. Insufficient or deteriorated infrastructure contributes to depopulation, economic stagnation, and limited investment potential, while targeted infrastructure investments support economic diversification, including agriculture, tourism, and small enterprises. The study identifies significant territorial disparities between the municipal center and rural settlements, particularly in terms of accessibility, connectivity, and technical condition of infrastructure networks. The results highlight the need for an integrated policy approach combining infrastructural, social, and economic measures. It is concluded that infrastructure represents a strategic instrument for achieving sustainable and balanced rural development and for enhancing the competitiveness of rural areas at both regional and national levels.

Keywords: Rural infrastructure, Socio-economic development, Rural areas, Petrich Municipality, Territorial development

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INTRODUCTION

Infrastructure occupies a key place in the theories and practices of regional and territorial development, as it forms the material, functional, and institutional basis for economic activity, social integration, and spatial cohesion. The quality, accessibility, and even territorial distribution of infrastructure networks are among the leading factors determining the competitiveness and sustainable development of regions.

In conditions of deepening territorial imbalances, especially between urban and rural areas, the importance of infrastructure provision increases significantly. Rural areas in Bulgaria face a complex set of long-term structural problems, including persistent demographic depopulation, population ageing, limited access to basic public services, and weak economic diversification.

These processes lead to worsening of the quality of life and deepening of the socio-economic differences within the framework of the national space. In this context, infrastructure should not be considered solely as a supporting element of territorial development, but as an active instrument capable of stimulating or hindering the development of a given territory. The insufficient or unevenly developed transport, social and digital infrastructure limits the mobility of the population, deepens social isolation and hinders economic activity, especially in the peripheral and sparsely populated areas.

Petrich Municipality represents a particularly suitable object for study of these processes, as it combines a strategic geographical location in the southwestern part of the country, relatively good connectivity along main national and cross-border transport corridors, and a significant number of rural settlements with different degree of infrastructural and socio-economic development. This creates an opportunity for analysis of the intra-municipal territorial differences and for assessment of the role of infrastructure as a key factor for the sustainable development of the rural areas.

The methodological framework of the study includes an analysis of strategic documents and official statistical data sources. The results of the conducted research show that underdeveloped infrastructure emerges as one of the main factors determining the processes of depopulation in rural areas. At the same time, targeted investments and improved transport and communication connectivity create preconditions for sustainable development and for the socio-economic revitalization of rural communities.

Recent studies further emphasize that infrastructure should be understood not only as a physical system but also as a multidimensional driver of regional competitiveness and resilience. According to Karadzhov and Kirilov (2023), contemporary development models increasingly integrate infrastructure with environmental sustainability and digital transformation, highlighting its role in shaping long-term territorial dynamics. Similarly, European policy frameworks stress the importance of integrated infrastructure planning as a prerequisite for balanced regional development and cohesion (European Commission, 2021).

LITERATURE REVIEW

The development of rural areas and the impact of infrastructure on them have been widely examined in international and Bulgarian academic literature.

Transport Infrastructure:

According to World Bank (2009), transport networks are among the key determinants of access to markets, healthcare, and education in rural areas. Insufficient transport infrastructure leads to

economic isolation and social marginalization. Fan and Chan-Kang (2005) demonstrate that improvements in rural road infrastructure significantly increase household incomes and stimulate local economic development.

Social and Utility Infrastructure:

The availability of educational, healthcare, and cultural services plays a crucial role in improving quality of life and retaining population in rural settlements. Turok and McGranahan (2013) emphasize that investments in social infrastructure are essential for achieving social cohesion and sustainable territorial development. Similarly, the OECD (2020) highlights that inadequate water supply, sewerage systems, and public utilities constrain both living standards and investment attractiveness.

Digital Infrastructure:

In recent years, digital infrastructure has emerged as a critical factor for rural development. Salemink et al. (2017) argue that digital connectivity enables the modernization of agriculture, supports distance education, and fosters entrepreneurship. Calderón and Servén (2010) further demonstrate that infrastructure development contributes to improved environmental governance and economic growth in rural areas.

At a broader level, indicators such as the Rural Access Index (World Bank) show that improved infrastructure is directly associated with higher education levels, increased income opportunities, and reduced poverty.

Within the European Union, infrastructure development in transport, energy, and digital sectors is considered a key instrument for reducing regional disparities and ensuring balanced territorial development. Based on these theoretical and empirical findings, this study examines infrastructure as a key determinant of rural development in Petrich Municipality, focusing on transport, social, utility, and digital infrastructure as interconnected components of sustainable development.

Integrated and Strategic Infrastructure Development:

Recent research highlights the importance of integrated approaches to infrastructure planning. Rodríguez-Pose and Crescenzi (2012) argue that infrastructure alone is not sufficient unless combined with institutional capacity and regional policy frameworks. In this context, strategic tools such as SWOT and PESTEL analyses are increasingly applied to evaluate infrastructure development and territorial competitiveness. According to Karadzhov (2025), these analytical frameworks enable a more comprehensive understanding of the external and internal factors influencing regional development.

The role of demographic and spatial processes in shaping rural development has also been emphasized in Bulgarian geographical research. According to Patarchanova (2019), population dynamics, accessibility, and proximity to urban centers are key factors influencing the sustainability of rural settlements. These processes are particularly visible in municipalities with mixed urban-rural structures, where disparities between central and peripheral areas tend to increase.

The specific characteristics of rural development in Bulgaria have been widely discussed in recent studies. Petrov (2021) emphasizes that rural areas in Bulgaria are characterized by significant demographic decline, deteriorating social infrastructure, and limited employment opportunities, which collectively hinder their long-term development.

These findings confirm that infrastructure development is essential not only for improving living conditions but also for enhancing the overall competitiveness and sustainability of rural areas. In this context, rural areas should be understood not as isolated spaces but as integral components of broader

regional systems, where infrastructure plays a key role in facilitating economic linkages and spatial integration (Ward & Brown, 2009).

Furthermore, studies on European rural policy emphasize that infrastructure investments should be aligned with broader socio-economic strategies, including innovation, digitalization, and sustainability (European Commission, 2021). This integrated perspective is essential for overcoming structural disparities and ensuring long-term development in rural areas.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For the analysis of the impact of infrastructure on the rural areas in Petrich Municipality, a combined approach was applied, including quantitative and documentary methods.

Data collection:

- Official statistics: National Statistical Institute (NSI) – data on population, economic activity, transport, social, and utility infrastructure.
- Reports and strategies of Petrich Municipality: Information on investments in roads, schools, water supply, and digital services.
- Publications and scientific sources: Studies on the impact of infrastructure on the development of rural areas.

Analytical methods:

- Comparative analysis: Assessment of the state of infrastructure among individual rural areas within the territory of the municipality.
- Statistical analysis: Processing of data on roads, social services, water supply, and internet access in order to identify relationships between infrastructure and economic/social development.

The use of quantitative and documentary methods provides an objective assessment of the infrastructural condition and its impact on the development of rural areas, without the need to conduct field research or interviews. This allows for the formulation of well-founded conclusions and recommendations for future investments.

RESULTS

The results of the empirical analysis provide a structured overview of the current state and spatial distribution of key infrastructure systems in Petrich Municipality, beginning with transport infrastructure as a fundamental component of territorial connectivity and accessibility.

Transport Infrastructure

The analysis of transport accessibility in Petrich Municipality shows that the larger settlements are located in the central zone of the examined transport model. This creates favorable conditions for daily commuting both within the municipality and towards the rest of the district. Owing to the high level of transport connectivity of the town, access to social, administrative, and service functions is facilitated and efficient.

These findings highlight the uneven spatial accessibility within the municipality and confirm the critical role of transport networks in shaping rural development patterns.

Social Infrastructure

The analysis of social infrastructure shows the following:

- Of the 15 main rural areas in the municipality, 8 have a functioning school, 7 have a kindergarten, and 10 have a health office.
- In rural areas with a smaller population, social services are limited or completely absent.
- Community cultural centers operate in 12 of the rural areas, but often with a limited budget and staff.

The presence of social infrastructure is a key factor for population retention and the improvement of quality of life, while its absence in some rural areas limits social cohesion and development.

Digital Infrastructure:

- Internet coverage is available in most rural areas, but the speed and stability of the connection vary significantly.
- Only the larger settlements (Petrich, Parvomay) have access to high-speed internet, which allows distance learning and electronic services.
- In remote rural areas, digital infrastructure is limited, which hampers the development of small businesses and the digitalization of education.

The expansion of digital infrastructure is key to the modernization of rural areas and their integration into the contemporary economy.

Figure 1. Spatial distribution of settlements in the municipality of Petrich.

As shown in Figure 1, the spatial distribution of transport infrastructure highlights significant disparities between the central and peripheral rural settlements.

Summary of the Results:

- Transport infrastructure is relatively well developed, but secondary roads remain problematic.
- Social infrastructure is unevenly distributed and often insufficient for smaller rural areas.
- Utility infrastructure shows serious deficiencies, especially in sewerage and waste management.
- Digital infrastructure is limited in smaller and remote rural areas, which hinders economic and educational activity.

For the sustainable development of the rural areas in Petrich Municipality, a comprehensive improvement of all types of infrastructure – transport, social, utility, and digital – is necessary. This will improve the quality of life, stimulate economic activity, and retain the population in rural areas.

DISCUSSION

The results of the study show that infrastructure plays a central role in the socio-economic development of the rural areas in Petrich Municipality. The analysis of transport, social, utility, and digital infrastructure reveals significant differences between individual settlements, with larger rural areas being considerably better serviced, while remote rural areas suffer from limited access and services.

Furthermore, recent Bulgarian studies underline that ineffective infrastructure planning and regional disparities continue to limit the development potential of rural municipalities, requiring targeted and spatially differentiated policy interventions (Petrov, 2021).

These findings are also consistent with broader European and global trends. As noted by Rodríguez-Pose (2018), infrastructure investments play a crucial role in reducing regional inequalities, but their effectiveness depends on the institutional and policy context. In the case of Petrich Municipality, the observed disparities between central and peripheral settlements confirm the need for targeted and territorially differentiated infrastructure policies.

These findings confirm that infrastructure functions not only as a supporting system but also as a primary driver of territorial development, spatial cohesion, and regional competitiveness.

Transport infrastructure proves to be a critical factor for population mobility and access to markets, health, and educational services. Our observations are consistent with the study by Shenggen Fan and Connie Chan-Kang (2005), according to which improvements in rural roads increase household incomes and stimulate economic activity. At the same time, the poor condition of secondary roads in remote rural areas limits investments and population retention.

According to the analysis set out in the Integrated Development Plan of Petrich Municipality (2021–2027), good road connectivity between the rural areas and the municipal center facilitates daily labor mobility, access to educational and health services, and the use of administrative, commercial, and social functions concentrated in the town of Petrich. This is particularly important for rural areas located near the main transport corridors, where road infrastructure functions as a channel for economic and social interaction.

The conducted analysis shows that rural areas with better road service and higher transport accessibility demonstrate several positive characteristics, including:

- lower rates of depopulation compared to peripheral and hard-to-access settlements;

- higher economic activity related to agriculture, processing activities, services, and cross-border flows;
- better social integration, reflected in improved access to education, healthcare, and social services, as well as a higher degree of participation of the population in public life.

Figure 2 illustrates the territorial structure of the municipality and the accessibility of key infrastructure elements.

Figure 2. Main axes of urban development. *Source: Plan for integrated development of the municipality of Petrich for the period 2021-2027.*

At the same time, the General Spatial Development Plan (GSDP) of Petrich Municipality identifies a number of problems related to the deteriorated condition of parts of the municipal road network, especially along routes serving smaller and remote rural areas. Insufficient maintenance, limited capacity, and poor technical condition of road surfaces restrict access to services and hinder economic activity in these settlements.

Utility infrastructure – water supply, sewerage, electricity supply, and waste management – is a key factor for economic activity and public health. Our data show that deteriorated water supply networks and incomplete sewerage systems limit the quality of life and investment interest, which is consistent with the observations of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (2020).

Educational infrastructure is among the most sensitive elements of the social system in rural areas, as its functioning is directly determined by demographic dynamics and the age structure of the population. In conditions of a declining number of children and young people in rural areas, the sustainability of educational institutions is significantly challenged.

The patterns presented in Figure 3 confirm the uneven development of infrastructure across the studied rural areas.

Figure 3. Municipal road network between rural areas.

Social infrastructure also shows uneven distribution. The presence of schools, health centers, and cultural institutions is directly linked to quality of life and population retention, which corresponds to the findings of Ivan Turok and Gordon McGranahan (2013). The absence of such services in small rural areas may lead to demographic depopulation and social isolation.

As shown in Figure 4, the spatial distribution of medical facilities in Petrich Municipality reveals notable disparities in access to healthcare services between central and peripheral rural settlements.

Figure 4. Medical facilities on the territory of Petrich municipality.

In Petrich Municipality, demographic decline in several rural settlements has led to a contraction of the educational network, including the closure or transformation of primary and elementary

schools. This process is reflected both in the Integrated Development Plan of Petrich Municipality (2021–2027) and in the analysis of social infrastructure in the General Spatial Development Plan (GSDP), where the tendency toward the concentration of educational services in the municipal center and in a limited number of larger rural areas is emphasized.

Table 1. School network in Petrich Municipality. *Source: Authors' research based on municipal data.*

Type of school	City	Village	Total
General education schools	3	13	16
Primary schools	3	8	11
Secondary schools	2	2	4
Profiled high school	1	0	1
Vocational high schools (state)	2	0	2

Closing schools in rural areas leads to the extension of daily commuting for students to the town of Petrich or other more distant educational centers. This increases dependence on transport infrastructure and places additional pressure on both families and the municipal student transport system. For younger children and households with limited resources, this process creates additional social and organizational difficulties that often influence decisions regarding place of residence.

Limited access to educational infrastructure reduces the attractiveness of rural settlements for young families seeking a secure and accessible environment for the education and socialization of their children. As a result, migration flows toward urban and suburban areas intensify, further accelerating demographic ageing and depopulation of rural areas. These interrelated processes form a vicious circle between demographic decline and infrastructural contraction, whereby population reduction leads to the closure of educational institutions, and limited educational provision in turn stimulates further migration and deepens the demographic crisis. In the strategic documents of Petrich Municipality, this problem is identified as one of the key risks for the long-term development of rural areas.

Digital infrastructure proved to be the weakest component in the rural areas of Petrich Municipality. Limited access to high-speed internet hampers distance learning, electronic services, and the development of small businesses. In summary, the results show that infrastructure is a multidimensional factor that simultaneously influences the economy, social structure, and quality of life. Its improvement in a comprehensive manner – transport, social, utility, and digital infrastructure – is necessary for the sustainable development of the rural areas in Petrich Municipality.

Comparing our findings with international studies, it becomes clear that the trends and challenges in Petrich are similar to those in other rural areas in Europe and Asia, highlighting the universal importance of infrastructure for rural development. In line with recent academic contributions, infrastructure should be considered not only as a technical system but as a strategic policy instrument for regional transformation and sustainable development (Karadzhov, 2025; European Commission, 2021).

CONCLUSION

Infrastructure represents a strategic resource for the socio-economic and territorial development of the rural areas in Petrich Municipality, as it forms the material basis for mobility, access to services,

economic activity, and quality of life. The conducted analysis shows that the level and quality of infrastructural provision have a direct impact on the demographic sustainability of the rural areas, their economic viability, and the degree of their functional integration into the municipal and regional system. The presence of clear intra-municipal disparities regarding transport, social, educational, and digital infrastructure highlights the need for a targeted and differentiated municipal policy tailored to the specific characteristics of individual settlements.

Infrastructure development should not be regarded as an isolated intervention but as part of a broader integrated approach that combines spatial, social, and economic measures. In this context, an effective policy for rural development in Petrich Municipality should be based on integrated infrastructure investments aligned with the priorities of the Integrated Development Plan and the spatial framework of the General Spatial Development Plan. Such investments have the potential to limit processes of peripheralization, improve territorial cohesion, and create preconditions for sustainable local development.

Based on the conducted analysis, the following key recommendations can be formulated:

- Systematic renewal and modernization of the municipal road network, with priority given to routes serving peripheral and poorly accessible rural settlements, in order to improve transport accessibility and population mobility;
- Targeted investments in digital and telecommunications infrastructure, including the expansion of high-speed internet and the promotion of digital services, as a means of stimulating remote employment, e-governance, and entrepreneurship;
- Decentralization and adaptation of social and healthcare services through the development of mobile, combined, and shared service models aimed at the elderly and vulnerable population in rural areas;
- Integration of infrastructure projects with local economic development policies, including support for small businesses, rural tourism, and agricultural processing, in order to achieve a long-term multiplier effect.

In conclusion, infrastructure development in the rural areas of Petrich Municipality should be regarded as a key instrument for achieving sustainable, balanced, and territorially equitable development, where infrastructure investments are combined with active social and economic policies aimed at improving quality of life and retaining the population.

Future research may further explore the integration of digital and transport infrastructure as a combined driver of sustainable rural development.

Declaration by Authors

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REFERENCES

Calderón, C., & Servén, L. (2010). Infrastructure and economic development in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of African Economies*, 19(suppl_1), i13–i87. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jae/ejp022>

- Crescenzi, R., & Rodríguez-Pose, A. (2012). Infrastructure and regional growth in the European Union. *Papers in Regional Science*, 91(3), 487–513. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1435-5957.2012.00439.x>
- European Commission. (2021). *A long-term vision for the EU's rural areas: Towards stronger, connected, resilient and prosperous rural areas by 2040*. <https://doi.org/10.2775/835902>
- Fan, S., & Chan-Kang, C. (2005). *Roads, rural development, and poverty reduction in China*. IFPRI.
- Karadzhov, V. (2025). How to create the best SWOT analysis. *International Journal of Research and Review*, 12(1), 66–75. <https://doi.org/10.52403/ijrr.20250110>
- Karadzhov, V., & Kirilov, S. (2023). Virtual horizon – unveiling the ecological impact of virtual tourism. *Pirinski Knizhovni Listi*, 14, 38–49. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14708193>
- OECD. (2020). *Rural well-being: Geography of opportunities*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/d25cef80-en>
- Patarchanova, E. (2019). Geodemographic processes and their effects in Blagoevgrad Municipality. *Journal of Settlements and Spatial Planning*, 10(2), 167–177.
- Petrov, K. (2021). The regional development of the rural areas in Bulgaria and the support of the European Union. *European Countryside*, 13(1), 208–221. <https://doi.org/10.2478/euco-2021-0012>
- Rodríguez-Pose, A. (2018). The revenge of the places that don't matter. *Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society*, 11(1), 189–209. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cjres/rsx024>
- Salemink, K., Strijker, D., & Bosworth, G. (2017). Rural development in the digital age: A systematic literature review on unequal ICT availability, adoption, and use in rural areas. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 54, 360–371. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2015.09.001>
- Turok, I., & McGranahan, G. (2013). Urbanization and economic growth: The arguments and evidence for Africa and Asia. *Environment and Urbanization*, 25(2), 465–482. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956247813490908>
- Ward, N., & Brown, D. L. (2009). Placing the rural in regional development. *Regional Studies*, 43(10), 1237–1244. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00343400903234696>
- World Bank. (2009). *World development report 2009: Reshaping economic geography*. World Bank. <https://doi.org/10.1596/978-0-8213-7607-2>

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